

Effect of pressure on the electronic structure of antiferromagnetic and paramagnetic YNiO_3 : role of disproportionation

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Abstract

The dependence of electronic properties of quantum materials on external knobs (e.g., pressure and temperature) is one of the fundamentals of neuromorphic computing, sensors, etc. Until recently, it has been believed that the theoretical description of such compounds cannot be accomplished using “traditional” density functional theory, and more advanced methods like dynamic mean-field theory should be utilized instead. Focusing here on the example of long-range ordered antiferromagnetic and paramagnetic YNiO_3 phases, we show the interplay between spin and structural motifs under pressure and their impact on electronic properties. We demonstrate a successful description of the insulating nature of both YNiO_3 phases and the role of symmetry-breaking motifs in the band gap opening. Moreover, by analyzing the pressure-dependent distribution of local motifs, we show that external pressure can significantly reduce the band gap energy of both phases, originating from the reduction of structural and magnetic disproportionation – change in the distribution of local motifs. These results thus demonstrate that some of the experimental observations in quantum materials (e.g., YNiO_3 compounds) can be fully understood without accounting for dynamic correlation.

23 Introduction

24 ABO₃ perovskites exhibit different degrees of spin and structural symmetry breaking¹⁻⁴, often defining
25 materials properties. At low temperatures, such motifs usually arrange in long-range ordered spin
26 magnetic configuration (i.e., antiferromagnetic, ferromagnetic, or nonmagnetic) with distinct
27 structural motifs (e.g., tilted octahedra or local dipole displacements). As temperature increases, the
28 ordered motifs may exhibit a significant change in their distribution, often leading to breaking of long-
29 range order⁵⁻⁸. For instance, YNiO₃ (one of the representative RNiO₃ compounds, where R is a rare-
30 earth element), under low temperatures (below 145 K), exists as α phase - an S-type ordered long-
31 range ordered antiferromagnet (AFM)^{9, 10} having a monoclinic crystal structure with two distinct NiO₆
32 octahedra. Upon heating, the α phase transforms isostructurally to the β phase - paramagnetic (PM)
33 insulator, which still has a distinct structural disproportionation¹¹. The paramagnetic properties of
34 YNiO₃ are stable at high temperatures, which was first shown in the measurement of temperature-
35 dependence of magnetic susceptibility by Demazeau et al⁹. They extrapolated the Curie-Weiss law to
36 temperatures below T_{Neel} and found the intersection of χ_M , corresponding to the Curie temperature,
37 to have a negative value of $T_{\text{Curie}} = -195$ K. At temperatures above 582 K, the PM monoclinic to PM
38 orthorhombic (β to γ) insulator-to-metal transition is observed¹⁰, accompanied by the suppression of
39 structural disproportionation. However, as noted in a recent review by Catalano et al.¹², various
40 experimental factors influence the exact value of the insulator-to-metal transition. A notable example
41 are the chemical doping effects introduced by oxygen vacancies, which induce extra electronic states
42 within the RNiO₃ band gap, causing a suppression of T_{MI} .

43 For a long time, it has been believed that mean-field density functional theory (DFT) cannot
44 describe the properties of such complex oxides, especially for PM phases¹³⁻²³. The evidence of such
45 belief has been that the nonmagnetic approximation of the PM β phase of RNiO₃ and other PM 3d
46 oxides could not capture the experimentally observed insulating properties of the compounds^{13-16, 18,}
47 ^{19, 21, 22}. Instead, it has been suggested that the properties of these oxides should be described from

48 the point of view of strongly correlated systems, where the metal-insulator transition is described in
49 terms of the ratio of electron-electron repulsion (U) and electronic bandwidth (W).^{14, 21, 22, 24-33}. Such a
50 correlated point of view has been used not only to explain the electronic properties of RNiO_3
51 compounds but also to describe the effect of external conditions (e.g., temperature and pressure) on
52 them³⁴⁻⁴⁰. Importantly in this picture, the distribution of local structural and spin motifs has not been
53 considered as the cause for band gap opening but rather ignored completely (e.g., model Hamiltonian
54 does not account for different local environments) or considered as the complementary follow-up
55 result of strong dynamic correlation.

56 With the recent development of symmetry broken density functional theory (S-DFT)^{5, 7, 8, 41-46},
57 it becomes clear that many of the experimental phenomena (e.g., band gap opening^{42, 47}, mass
58 enhancement⁴⁸, orbital ordering⁴) can be well explained within S-DFT without additional accounting
59 for U/W ratio as long as the system is allowed to develop energy lowering structural and spin symmetry
60 breaking – “correct” distribution of local motifs. In this way, the given property of the compound is
61 described as a superposition of properties of local motifs instead of the single property of the global
62 average motif. The successful application of S-DFT to the α and β phases of YNiO_3 has been
63 demonstrated^{6, 42, 49} recently. However, it still remains unclear whether S-DFT can describe the effect
64 of external conditions on the electronic properties of YNiO_3 . Motivated by this, we further explore if
65 accounting for the dynamic correlation effect is needed to explain the effect of pressure on the
66 electronic properties of the α and β phases of YNiO_3 .

67

68 Results

69 Band gap opening in α and β YNiO_3 phases within DFT

70 Similar to previous works^{6, 45, 46}, we find that allowing for a spin and structural symmetry breaking (i.e.,
71 using complex S-type AFM and spin quasi-random⁵⁰ spin distribution for the monoclinic structure of α

72 and β phases, respectively) is sufficient to reproduce the properties of the YNiO_3 phases (Fig. 1). The
73 S-type AFM order was adapted following the work of Varignon et al., who have shown that this spin
74 arrangement produces the lowest-energy structure of YNiO_3 ⁴⁹. Specifically, we observe a clear
75 disproportionation of NiO_6 octahedra - the volumes for small and large octahedra are 9.07/10.69 \AA^3
76 in the α phase and $9.16 \pm 0.04 / 10.61 \pm 0.05 \text{\AA}^3$ in the β phase. For both phases, local magnetic moments
77 on nickel atoms show a zero-centered distribution with three distinct peaks. One is centered at 0 (low
78 spin state), and the other two at approximately $\pm 1.4 \mu_B$ (high spin state). The low and high spin states
79 correspond exactly to the small and large octahedra sublattices, respectively. One difference between
80 results for the α and β phases is the existence of a broader distribution of local structural/magnetic
81 motifs than those for α phase (Fig. S1). The total magnetic moment (i.e., $\sum_i^n \mu_i$), however, remains zero
82 (Fig. 1). We note that in contrast to the nonmagnetic (NM) approximation of PM β phase, the spin
83 polymorphous approach allows reproducing the insulating phase (Fig. 1d). While there are no
84 experimental data on measurements of magnetic moments in β phase, Alonso et al. reported that
85 neutron powder diffraction experimental data for α phase can be understood as the existence of two
86 Ni sublattices with different magnetic moments (i.e., 1.4 and 0.7 μ_B)¹⁰. The formation of different local
87 spin/structural motifs is a necessary condition to open the gap in YNiO_3 phases. For instance, Dalpian
88 et al. demonstrated that the formation of two octahedra results in the splitting of metallic states,
89 leading to band gap opening⁵¹. The authors explained the mechanism of band gap opening as
90 following: Owing to the shorter bond distances, the hybrid levels of the small octahedra are pushed to
91 higher energy, while for the large octahedra, the coupling is weaker, leading to weaker repulsion. The
92 final effect is that holes are pushed to higher energies, and electrons are pushed to lower energies.
93 When the difference in the strength of the coupling for small and large octahedra is large enough, the
94 band gap opening is observed. This physical picture is further confirmed by other research works.^{6, 42,}

95 ⁴⁵

96

97 **Figure 1.** (top panels) Distribution of local spin and structural motifs in (a) α - (antiferromagnetic) and (b) β -
 98 (paramagnetic) YNiO_3 phases and their effect on (bottom panels) electronic properties and density of states
 99 projection on Y-d (black line), Ni-d (blue line), and O-p (red line) valence orbitals.

100

101 Pressure dependence of band gap, structural and magnetic motifs in α and β YNiO_3
 102 phases

103 Upon pressure, both α and β phases of YNiO_3 show the band gap reduction with pressure increase
 104 (Fig. 2). For instance, SCAN band gap energy for the β (α) phase of YNiO_3 under 0 GPa is 0.62 eV (1.01
 105 eV), while the band gap energy under 20 GPa decreases to 0.50 eV (0.94 eV). Under reduced pressure,
 106 the band gap opens further up to 0.70 eV (1.03 eV) under -20 GPa. The band gap dependence on
 107 pressure is found to be linear within the calculated range. These results are consistent with available
 108 experimental results³⁹ showing a reduction of resistivity of α and β phases upon external pressure. To
 109 better understand the evolution of electronic properties, we explore the effect of pressure on
 110 structural and spin local motifs. The main results are:

111

112 **Figure 2.** Pressure dependence of electronic band gap of α (antiferromagnetic) and β (paramagnetic) YNiO_3
 113 phases.

114

115 (i) We find that α and β phases have a monoclinic crystal symmetry (space group $P2_1/n$, space group
 116 (SG): 14) in the considered pressure range. The computed X-ray diffraction (XRD) spectra are in good
 117 agreement with experimental diffractograms measured by Alonso et al.¹¹ in terms of the position of
 118 peaks and lattice parameters (Fig. S1). We note, however, that the experimental data available for
 119 comparison is sparse. This is due to the low magnitude of monoclinic distortion in YNiO_3 , which is
 120 beyond the detection limit of XRD techniques with conventional laboratory-scale X-ray sources.
 121 Synchrotron XRD (SXR) or neutron diffraction is required to discern it and observe the structural
 122 disproportionation described below⁵². The pressure effect can be generally summarized as the right
 123 shift of the main characteristic SXR peaks (Fig. S1). For example, the behavior with the pressure of
 124 the signal originating from the (116) plane was identified as the tell-tale sign of the change of dominant
 125 phase present in YNiO_3 samples of Garcia-Muñoz et al.⁵³. In that experiment, a single distinct peak was

126 observed below and above the phase transition, and a double peak structure at an intermediate
127 pressure close to the transition. Its position shifts from 20.78° to 20.86° at pressures 12.5 and 13.9
128 GPa, which are below and above the transition, respectively. In our data, the (116) signal exhibits a
129 split-peak structure across all analyzed pressures. We attribute this to the fact that computed data
130 precisely reproduces the ground state and is presented without any additional symmetry refinement.
131 It is also notable that in our DFT calculations no temperature effects are taken into consideration,
132 which may result in the merging of this two-peak signal into a single one. Its position shifts from
133 $2\theta=20.49^\circ$ at 0 GPa to $2\theta=20.98^\circ$ at 20 GPa pressure (Fig. S3). The peak position at 14 GPa is $2\theta=20.85^\circ$,
134 which is in excellent agreement with the 13.9 GPa values reported by Garcia-Muñoz et al.⁵³.

135 (ii) At all considered pressures, we observe the presence of small and large NiO_6 octahedra (Fig. 3) – a
136 distinguishable feature that determines the monoclinic $P2_1/n$ structure. To describe the pressure
137 effect on structural properties, we define the degree of structural disproportionation (Δ_V) as the
138 difference between mean values of small and large octahedral volumes, $\Delta_V = \langle V_L \rangle - \langle V_S \rangle$. At 0 GPa,
139 the α (β) phase shows Δ_V of 1.61 \AA^3 (1.45 \AA^3). Under pressure, it changes monotonically, and at 20
140 GPa the value shifts to 1.15 \AA^3 (1.03 \AA^3). At negative pressures, the degree of structural
141 disproportionation rises to 2.75 \AA^3 (2.55 \AA^3). Thus, over the whole range of pressures, the α phase
142 shows slightly higher disproportionation than the β phase (Fig. 3a). These results thus demonstrate
143 that the structural disproportionation is not suppressed in any of the phases as the result of pressure
144 alone, which is in line with available experimental results^{10, 11, 54-56}.

145 (iii) We find the existence of different magnetic motifs with a clear presence of magnetic
146 disproportionation manifested by the formation of high and low-spin NiO_6 octahedra for all considered
147 pressures. This magnetic disproportionation originates from Ni sublattices – the magnetic moments
148 on O and Y atoms are nil within the projection accuracy. To better quantify the distribution of local
149 magnetic motifs, we calculate the degree of magnetic disproportionation as the difference between
150 mean absolute values of the high-spin and low-spin magnetic moment distributions on Ni sublattices,

151 $\Delta_M = \langle |\mu_L| \rangle - \langle |\mu_S| \rangle$. In the case of α and β -YNiO₃ phases, these moments correspond to the Ni sites
152 in the centers of large and small NiO₆ octahedra, respectively. For both α and β phases, Δ_M vs P follows
153 a linear trend for α and β phases with a similar slope, i.e., the degree of disproportionation increases
154 to 1.35 and 1.32 μ_B at 20 GPa to 1.56 and 1.54 μ_B at -20 GPa for α and β phase, respectively. These
155 results thus demonstrate the similarity of pressure dependence of local magnetic motifs for the two
156 phases and more importantly indicate that under all pressure β -YNiO₃ phase has non-zero magnetic
157 moments.

158

159 **Figure 3.** (a) Pressure-dependent distribution of local motifs in α (antiferromagnetic) and β (paramagnetic)
 160 YNiO_3 phases. Structural disproportionation factor Δ_V is defined as the difference between mean volumes of
 161 large (V_L) and small (V_S) NiO_6 octahedra, magnetic disproportionation factor Δ_M is defined as the difference
 162 between mean absolute values of high-spin (centered on large octahedra, μ_L) and low-spin (centered on small
 163 octahedra, μ_S) distributions on the Ni sublattice. (b) Pressure dependence of the two disproportionation factors.

164

165 Discussion

166 In summary, we demonstrated that the experimentally observed pressure-dependent electronic
167 properties can be described entirely within mean-field DFT without accounting of dynamic correlation
168 or a more general interpretation of the effect in the language of U/W ratio. Within DFT, we confirm
169 that Ni in large (Ni_L) and small (Ni_S) octahedra contribute differently to band edges. Ni_S and Ni_L
170 contribute to conduction and valence states (Fig. S2), respectively. As pressure increases, the small
171 and large octahedra become alike to each other (less disproportionated) which results in band gap
172 reduction. Qualitatively, the same trends are obtained using SCAN without the U correction and
173 different variants of U-corrected PBE density functionals (Fig. S3). This shows that the U correction is
174 not necessary to produce a band gap and disproportionated structure of YNiO_3 . Thus the SCAN
175 functional represents the minimal level of density functional theory that can be used to capture the
176 electronic properties without any fitted parameters. These results thus further extend the scenario of
177 band gap opening proposed by Dalpian et al.⁵¹. The pressure increase mainly affects the strength of
178 the coupling of hybridized states for small and large octahedra, reducing the band gap as octahedral
179 disproportionation is lowered. Moreover, there is no fundamental difference in the pressure
180 dependence of the electronic properties between α and β - YNiO_3 . Thus, the change of electronic
181 properties of both phases originates from the change of local motifs' distribution and their
182 contribution to the electronic structure. This physical picture is different from that discussed in
183 literature that explains the observed effects in the language of strong electron correlation³⁴⁻⁴⁰, where
184 U/W ratio change was considered as the underlying cause rather than the structural changes
185 themselves. While we demonstrate the difference in the physical understanding of pressure-
186 dependent electronic properties, our results on the structural changes are consistent with the
187 experiment. For instance, Ramos et al. demonstrated that at room temperature, pressure results in
188 the opening of the octahedral tilting angle⁴⁰. According to our results, the tilting angle is a structural
189 property correlated to the degree of disproportionation at least when different local motifs are

190 allowed to develop as long as they lower the internal energy of the system. For instance, within such
191 energy minimization approach the average tilting angle for α and β -YNiO₃ phases increases from
192 147.81° and 147.75° at 0 GPa to 149.18° and 149.06° at 20 GPa, respectively. These results thus
193 demonstrate that pressure-dependence of electronic properties is largely originated from change of
194 distribution of local structural/spin motifs.

195 Methods

196 Planewave DFT calculations have been performed using VASP⁵⁷⁻⁶⁰ with PAW pseudopotentials⁶¹
197 and meta-GGA-type SCAN functional⁶². The cutoff energy was set to 500 and 550 eV for final relaxation
198 and volume optimization calculations, respectively. Density of the Γ -centered k-point grid was set to
199 1000 (10000) per reciprocal atom for initial and final relaxation, respectively. The effect of pressure
200 was modeled via the application of homogeneous isotropic pressure. The relaxation was performed
201 until the force on each atom was smaller than 0.01 eV/Å. The α phase of YNiO₃ was modeled as
202 AFM-S spin arrangement in an 80-atom cell of a monoclinic phase of YNiO₃. The β phase of YNiO₃ was
203 described using spin polymorphous model of PM phase^{41, 42, 45, 63} with a 160-atom cell, where spin
204 distribution corresponds to spin quasi-random structure (high-temperature limit of paramagnets). The
205 data were analyzed and visualized using Python Materials Genomics (pymatgen) code⁶⁴ and Vesta⁶⁵.

206

207 Data Availability

208 The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the
209 corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

210

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223 Contributions

224 M.W. did all calculations, prepared the figures, and performed part of the data analysis. O.I.M.
225 suggested the problem, guided the data analysis, and directed the writing of the text with
226 contributions from M.W.

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230 Competing interests

231 The authors declare no competing financial or non-financial interests.

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